

MFAing the Quantum Crypto Proof Mobile Apps

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Abstract

With the advent of Quantum Computing, special care needs to be drawn upon the fact that powerful Quantum Computers will be able to crack traditional (PKI) security schemes used today on the Web. Google's CEO, Sundar Pichai, was quoted as predicting at the World Economic Forum in Davos that quantum computers will spell the end of standard encryption within five to ten years. While many alternatives exist, Web based Identity Management still rely heavily on User-ID, Password combo. The Federated Identity Management (FIM) has brought some relief in form Single-Sign-On (SSO) and Single-Log-Out (SLO) but still, the user has to remember ever increasing lengths and more difficult to remember characters in their passwords. The Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) is well suited panacea for such problematics when combined with Smart Phone used as Universal Authentication Device.

IDENTITY THEFT

According to Microsoft [1] some 1.2 million Azure Active Directory accounts are compromised every month. This could be avoided with Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) that Microsoft also provides out-of-the-box [2]. The uptake of such evolution would necessitate the End Users in taking more responsible attitude towards IT security. It is a common belief that strong security is the enemy of simple and convenient User Experience (UX). In these matters CSOs and CISOs might hesitate to impose too strict security policies that affect all levels of the organisation up-to the CEO. Nevertheless, it is thanks to the modern Online Banking applications that new Smart Phone based authentication mechanism may end-up in main stream sooner or later in all kinds of Web and Mobile application use cases.

CURRENT OPTIONS FOR MFA

Nowadays we can list altogether some five different factors for prospective MFA authentication schemes according to Medium.com [3]. These are:

1. Something you know
2. Something you have
3. Something you are
4. Somewhere you are
5. Something you do

The first case is the simple UID, PWD combo discussed earlier, the second is eg. security token in form of time limited one-time password (TOTP, HOTP), the third relates to biometrics of various kinds (Fingerprint, Voice or Face print, Retina scan), the fourth is based on IP Geolocation information, or GPS coordinates of the Mobile device, and finally the fifth is about gestures on touch screens such as swipes or signatures.

LATEST DEVELOPMENTS

The most secure options for enabling MFA in Administrative security elevated (eg. ISO27001) tasks has been the provision of RSA SecureID or Deepnet SafeID like dongles that produce secure random number of limited lifetime TOTP or HOTP. Typically, these dongles are inserted to the USB port of the PC or Laptop for operation with LCD screen showing generated number. More recently Yubikey for Mobile provides similar functionality through NFC or USB-C connectivity directly to your Mobile phone. This Spring ID Quantique and SK Telecom announced [4] the availability of Quantum Random Number Generator (QRNG) equipped Samsung A71 5G smart phone model, that can provide very safe TOTP keys.

FUTURE WORK

Quantum cryptography is based on Quantum Physics and the physical properties of Photons. In addition to Quantum Random Number Generation (QRNG), also concepts of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) can be used for securing data in transit over fibre optic connections. In Future, symmetric encryption keys are preferred over asymmetric ones, which gives room to deploy also bit older technologies such as Shamir's Secret Sharing Scheme (SSSS) [5] for split encryption keys over several key-store media (e.g. NFC dongles) to recover the Quantum Random Number Generated master key if necessary. This way the unique key-store will not become the Single Point of Failure (SPOF) and the master key can be recovered providing added redundancy or delegated responsibility to key-store holders at large.

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